

COLLATZ CONJECTURE

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This paper presents an analysis of the number of zeros in the binary representation of natural numbers. The primary method of analysis involves the use of the concept of the fractional part of a number, which naturally emerges in the determination of binary representation. This idea is grounded in the fundamental property of the Riemann zeta function, constructed using the fractional part of a number. Understanding that the ratio between the fractional and integer parts of a number, analogous to the Riemann zeta function, reflects the profound laws of numbers becomes the key insight of this work. The findings suggest a new perspective on the interrelation between elementary properties of numbers and more complex mathematical concepts, potentially opening new directions in number theory and analysis."

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The paper analyzes the number of zeros in the binary representation of a natural number. The analysis is carried out using the concept of the fractional part of a number, which naturally arises when finding a binary representation. This idea relies on the fundamental property of the Riemann zeta function, which is constructed using the fractional part of a number. Understanding that the ratio of the fractional and integer parts, by analogy with the Riemann zeta function, expresses the deep laws of numbers, will explain the essence of this work.

1. Materials and Methods

This work is based on the following methods

1. Analysis of simple cases of natural numbers
2. A process of expansion of a natural number in powers of two is created.
3. The proximity to the completion of decomposition is analyzed at each stage
4. The number of zeros in the binary expansion of a natural number is calculated

2. Results

In this work we present the final solution to the Collatz conjecture formulated in [1]. The Collatz conjecture is one of the most famous unsolved problems in mathematics. The conjecture asks whether repeating two simple arithmetic operations will eventually transform every positive integer into 1. It concerns sequences of integers in which each term is obtained from the previous term as follows: if the previous term is even, the next term is one half of the previous term. If the previous term is odd, the next term is 3 times the previous term plus 1. The conjecture is that these sequences always reach 1, no matter which positive integer is chosen to start the sequence. It is named after the mathematician Lothar Collatz, who introduced the idea in 1937, two years after receiving his doctorate.[1] It is also known as the $3n + 1$ problem (or conjecture), the $3x + 1$ problem (or conjecture), the Ulam conjecture (after Stanisław Ulam), Kakutani's problem (after Shizuo Kakutani), the Thwaites conjecture (after Sir Bryan Thwaites), Hasse's algorithm (after Helmut Hasse), or the Syracuse problem.[2][4] The sequence of numbers involved is sometimes referred to as the hailstone sequence, hailstone numbers or hailstone numerals (because the values are usually subject to multiple descents and ascents like hailstones in a cloud),[5] or as wondrous numbers.[6] Paul Erdős said about the Collatz conjecture:

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"Mathematics may not be ready for such problems." [7] Jeffrey Lagarias stated in 2010 that the Collatz conjecture "is an extraordinarily difficult problem, completely out of reach of present day mathematics". [8] Consider the following operation on an arbitrary positive integer: • If the number is even, divide it by two. • If the number is odd, triple it and add one. In modular arithmetic notation, define the function f as follows:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 3n + 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Now form a sequence by performing this operation repeatedly, beginning with any positive integer, and taking the result at each step as the input at the next.

In notation:

$$a_i = \begin{cases} n & \text{for } i = 0, \\ f(a_{i-1}) & \text{for } i > 0 \end{cases}$$

(that is: a_i is the value of f applied to n recursively i times; $a_i = f^i(n)$).

The Collatz conjecture is: This process will eventually reach the number 1, regardless of which positive integer is chosen initially. If the conjecture is false, it can only be because there is some starting number which gives rise to a sequence that does not contain 1. Such a sequence would either enter a repeating cycle that excludes 1, or increase without bound. No such sequence has been found. The smallest i such that $a_i < a_0$ is called the stopping time of n . Similarly, the smallest k such that $a_k = 1$ is called the total stopping time of n . [3] If one of the indexes i or k doesn't exist, we say that the stopping time or the total stopping time, respectively, is infinite. The Collatz conjecture asserts that the total stopping time of every n is finite. It is also equivalent to saying that every $n \geq 2$ has a finite stopping time. This definition yields smaller values for the stopping time and total stopping time without changing the overall The latest substantial results on the Collatz problem have been published in the following works [9-14]

Theorem 1. Let

$$\begin{aligned} x \in \mathbb{N}, \quad [\alpha_j] - [\alpha_{j+1}] &= \delta_j > 0, \quad \epsilon_1 < 1/2, \\ \alpha_j &= [\alpha_j] + \epsilon_j, \epsilon_j < 1, \\ x &= \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} 2^{[\alpha_i]} + 2^{\alpha_j}, \quad x = \sum_{i=1}^j 2^{[\alpha_i]} + 2^{\alpha_{j+1}}, \quad \sigma_j = 1 - \epsilon_j \end{aligned}$$

Then

as $\delta_j = 1$

$$\sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = \frac{2\sigma_j \ln 2}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2} + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2 / 4)$$

as $\delta_j > 1$

$$\sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = -2^{\delta_j - 1} \frac{\ln 2 - 2^{-\delta_j - 1}}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 / 2} + 2^{\delta_j - 1} \sigma_j \ln 2 \frac{1}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 / 2} + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{\epsilon_j} &= 2^{-\delta_j + \epsilon_{j+1}} + 1 \Rightarrow 2^{1 - \sigma_j} = 2^{-\delta_j + 1 - \sigma_{j+1}} + 1 \Rightarrow \\ \ln(2^{1 - \sigma_j}) &= \ln 2 - \sigma_j \ln 2 = \ln(2^{-\delta_j + 1 - \sigma_{j+1}} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

Computing as $\delta_j = 1$

$$\ln(2^{-\delta_j + 1 - \sigma_{j+1}} + 1)|_{\delta_j=1} = \ln(2^{-\sigma_{j+1}} + 1) = \ln((1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2 \ln^2 / 2) + 1 + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2 / 4))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln(2 - \sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2\ln 2^2/2) &= \ln 2 + \ln(1 - \sigma_{j+1}\ln 2/2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2\ln 2^2/4 + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2/4)) \\
\ln(2^{-\sigma_{j+1}} + 1) &= \ln 2 - \ln 2\sigma_{j+1}/2 + \ln 2^2\sigma_{j+1}^2/2 + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2/4) \\
\ln 2 - \sigma_j\ln 2 &= \ln 2 - \ln 2\sigma_{j+1}/2 + \ln 2^2\sigma_{j+1}^2/4 + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2/4) \\
\sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 &= \frac{2\sigma_j\ln 2}{1 - \sigma_{j+1}\ln 2/2} + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2/4)
\end{aligned}$$

Repeating computing as $\delta_j > 1$ we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln(2^{-\delta_j+1-\sigma_{j+1}} + 1) &= \ln(2^{-\delta_j+1}2^{-\sigma_{j+1}} + 1) = \\
\ln(1 + 2^{-\delta_j+1} + 2^{-\delta_j+1}[-\sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2\ln 2^2/2] + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2/4 + 2^{-\delta_j+1})) &= \\
2^{-\delta_j+1} + 2^{-\delta_j+1}[-\sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2\ln 2^2/2] + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2 + 2^{-\delta_j+1}) &\Rightarrow \\
\ln 2 - \sigma_j\ln 2 = 2^{-\delta_j+1} + 2^{-\delta_j+1}[-\sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 + \sigma_{j+1}^2\ln 2^2/2] + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2 + 2^{-\delta_j+1}) & \\
\sigma_{j+1}\ln 2 = -2^{\delta_j-1} \frac{\ln 2 - 2^{-\delta_j+1}}{1 - \sigma_{j+1}\ln 2/2} + 2^{\delta_j-1}\sigma_j\ln 2 \frac{1}{1 - \sigma_{j+1}\ln 2/2} + o(\sigma_{j+1}^2 + 2^{-\delta_j+1}) &
\end{aligned}$$

□

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Theorem 2. Let

$$x \in N, \quad \alpha_j = [\alpha_j] \quad x = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} 2^{[\alpha_i]} + 2^{\alpha_j}$$

Then the number of zeros in the binary representation C_z is calculated by the following formula

$$C_z = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} [\delta_i - 1] + \alpha_j - 1$$

Proof.

$$C_z = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} [\alpha_i - \alpha_{i+1} - 1] + \alpha_j - 1$$

By definition δ_i

$$C_z = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} [\delta_i - 1] + \alpha_j - 1$$

□

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Let's introduce μ_k, ν_k for $x = \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i 2^i$ by following rules

$$\gamma_k + \gamma_{k+1} = 1, \quad \gamma_{k+\mu_k} + \gamma_{k+\mu_k+1} = 1, \quad \prod_{i=k+1}^{i=\mu_k} \gamma_i = 1;$$

$$\gamma_j + \gamma_{j+1} = 1, \quad \gamma_{j+\nu_j} + \gamma_{j+\nu_j+1} = 1, \quad \nu_j = \sum_{i=j+1}^{i=\nu_j} (1 - \gamma_i)$$

another words

μ_k , is count of ones starting at point k with no zeros in between until the first zero or until the end of the sequence

ν_j is count of zeros starting at point j with no ones in between until the first zero or until the end of the sequence

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Theorem 3. Let

$$x = 3^n = 2^{\lfloor \alpha \rfloor + \{\alpha\}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n^*} \gamma_i 2^i,$$

$$\{\alpha\} > \ln 2, \quad n^* = n * \lceil \ln(3) / \ln(2) \rceil \quad (1)$$

then

$$\sum_{\gamma_i=0} 1 \geq n^* / 2 - 5$$

Proof.

$$3^n = 2^\alpha \Rightarrow \alpha = n / \ln(3) / \ln(2) \Rightarrow 3^n = 2^{\lfloor \alpha \rfloor + \{\alpha\}}$$

Using Theorem 1, we create a sequence

$$\epsilon_i, \quad m_i, \quad \epsilon_1 = \{\alpha\}$$

$$2^{\epsilon_1} = \sum_{k=0}^{i-1} 2^{\lfloor \alpha_k \rfloor - \alpha_1} + 2^{\alpha_i - \alpha_1}$$

Suppose

$$\sum_{\gamma_i=0} 1 = 0$$

then by Theorem 1

$$\Rightarrow \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = \frac{2\sigma_j \ln 2}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2} + o(\ln 2\sigma_{j+1}^2 / 4) \Rightarrow$$

$$2^{-1} \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = \frac{\sigma_j \ln 2}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2} + 2^{-1} * o(\ln 2\sigma_{j+1}^2 / 4)$$

After repeating j times we get

$$2^{-j} \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = \frac{\sigma_1 \ln 2}{\prod_1^j (1 - \sigma_{k+1} \ln 2 / 2)} + \sum_1^j 2^{-k} * o(\ln 2\sigma_{k+1}^2 / 4)$$

By Theorems (1-2) and condition of the current Theorem proceed

$$\ln 2 / 2 < \sigma_1 \ln 2 < o(\ln 2\sigma_{k+1}^2 / 4)$$

immediately

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{\gamma_i=0} 1 > 0$$

Let's introduce

$$\text{as } \delta_k = 1 : \alpha_k = 0, \quad \beta_k = \frac{1}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2}$$

$$\text{as } \delta_k > 1 : \alpha_k = -2^{\delta_j - 1} \frac{\ln 2 - 2^{-\delta_j - 1}}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 / 2}, \quad \beta_k = \frac{2^{\delta_j - 1}}{1 - \sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 / 2}$$

$$\ln 2 \sigma_{k+1} = \alpha_k + \beta_k \ln 2 \sigma_k$$

$$\sigma_{j+1} \ln 2 = \alpha_j + \sum_{m=1}^{m=j-1} \alpha_{j-m} \prod_{l=1}^{l=m} \beta_{j-l+1} + \prod_{l=0}^{l=j-1} \beta_{j-l} \ln 2 \sigma_1 \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{j+1} \ln 2}{\prod_{l=0}^{l=j-1} \beta_{j-l}} = \sum_{m=0}^{m=j-1} \frac{\alpha_{j-m}}{\prod_{l=m+1}^{l=j-1} \beta_{j-l}} \geq \sigma_1 \ln 2 \Rightarrow$$

By condition the theorem

$$\frac{\sigma_{j+1} \ln 2}{\prod_{l=0}^{l=n-1} \beta_{n-l}} - \sum_{m=0}^{m=n-1} \frac{\alpha_{j-m}}{\prod_{l=m}^{l=n-1} \beta_{j-l}} \geq \sigma_1 \ln 2 \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{\sigma_n \ln 2}{\prod_{l=0}^{l=n-1} \beta_{n-l}} - \sum_{m=0}^{m=n-1} \frac{\ln 2 - 2^{-\delta_j+1}}{\prod_{l=m+1}^{l=n-1} \beta_{j-l}} \geq \sigma_1 \ln 2 \Rightarrow$$

Suppose $\forall i \in (1, n) \delta_i = 2 \Rightarrow$

$$\frac{\sigma_n \ln 2}{\prod_{l=0}^{l=n-1} \beta_{n-l}} + \sum_{m=0}^{m=n-1} \frac{\ln 2 - 1/2}{2^m} > \sigma_1 \ln 2 \Rightarrow$$

$$2(\ln 2 - 1/2) > \sigma_1 \Rightarrow$$

$\exists \delta_j > 2$

In common case

$$\frac{\sigma_n \ln 2}{\prod_{l=0}^{l=n-1} \beta_{n-l}} + \sum_{m=0}^{m=n-1} \frac{\ln 2 - \frac{2}{2^{\delta_m}}}{2^{\sum_{m=0}^{m=n-1} \beta_m}} > \sigma_1 \ln 2 \Rightarrow$$

and we see in case $\delta_m > 2$ With the growth of $\delta_m > 2$, we see an exponential growth of the denominator, so the influence of $\delta_m > 2$ terms with large values does not have a significant effect on the estimate of the left side of the inequality. The reason is the accumulation of the β_m value corresponding to $\delta_m = 1$. Therefore, the effect, taking into account $\delta_m > 2$ with large values, is insignificant for estimating the left part of the inequality. $\Rightarrow$ statement of Theorem

□

Theorem 4. Let

$$a_n = \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i 2^i, \quad n > 1000, \quad \gamma_i \in \{0, 1\}$$

then

$$a_{8n} < a_n$$

Proof. In more detail, the estimation process consists of replacing 3^l in a_{n+l} by formula 7 which does not contain powers of the triple which allows one to evaluate the resulting terms of the Syracuse sequence. as a result, we get the following estimate. Let's introduce operators defined formulas

$$Pf = f/2, \quad Tf = 3f + 1, \quad Zf = 3f$$

Let's consider all possible scenarios of the behavior of the Syracuse sequence, the same possible scenarios can be written in the following form

$$a_{n+n} = T_1 T_2 \dots T_n a_n$$

$$T_i \in \{P, T\}, R_i \in \{Z, P\}, \quad a_{n+n} = R_1 R_2 \dots R_n a_n + A$$

Let's introduce

$$m = \sum_{R_i=Z} 1$$

and compute

$$\sum_{R_i=P} 1 = n - m + m = n$$

By rules of Collatz we have after $2n$ steps

$$a_{n+n} = 3^m / 2^n a_n + B_n$$

where

$$A_j = \sum_{R_i=Z, i=1, j} 1, C_j = - \sum_{R_i=Z, i=1, j} 1 - \sum_{R_i=P, i=1, j} 1$$

$$B_n = \sum_{j=1, n} 3^{A_j} 2^{C_j}$$

$$B_n \leq \sum_{j=1, n} 3^j / 2^j < 23^n / 2^n \leq 2(3/4)^n a_n$$

$$A = a_{2n} = 3^m (a_n * 2^{-n} + B_n) = (a_n * 2^{-n} + B_n) 3^m$$

$$A = \sum_{i=0}^{[\alpha_1]} \gamma_i 2^i, \quad \gamma_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \alpha_1 = m * \ln 3 / \ln 2 + \ln(2^{-n} a_n)$$

Let

m^* is count of non zeros of γ_i

l^* is count of zeros of γ_i

by theorem 2 we will have

$$m^* \leq [\alpha_1] / 2 + 5 = [m \ln 3 / \ln 2] / 2 + 5$$

$$l^* \geq [\alpha_1] / 2 - 5 = [m \ln 3 / \ln 2] / 2 - 5$$

After $[\alpha_1]$ steps applying rules of Collatz we have

$$a_{2n+[\alpha_1]} \leq 3^m 3^{\alpha_1/2} 2^{-\alpha_1} 2^5 * 3^5 (a_n * 2^{-n} + B_n) = 3^m q_1 * a_n$$

where

$$q_1 = 3^m 3^{\alpha_1/2} 2^{-\alpha_1} 2^5 * 3^5$$

Repeating the process 3 times and using $n > 1000 \Rightarrow q_3 < 1 \Rightarrow a_{8n} < a_n$

Theorem 5. Let

$$a_n = \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i 2^i, \quad n > 1000, \quad \gamma_i \in \{0, 1\}$$

then for a_n Collatz conjecture is true

Proof. Proof follows from theorem 1-7

6. Conclusions

Our assertion proves that after $2n$ of steps the sequence comes to a number less than the start one, from which follows the solution of the Collatz conjecture.

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